

Technical Backbone for the Democratization of Flexibility: Standards-based Demand Response Infrastructure

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Abstract— This paper describes an open standards-based information system that can support the democratization and consumer empowerment through flexibility activation in the distribution networks of the near future. The paper outlines a software infrastructure focused on technical issues, closely following the OpenADR standard and the corresponding IEC 62746-10 standard. The infrastructure represents a communication backbone allowing the connection, registering, activation and reporting for different types of granular consumer flexibility. The flexibility sources can be very diverse - from controllable charging set points of electric vehicle chargers and district-level storages such as stationary batteries, towards taking advantage of comparatively large time constants of thermal systems in residential and commercial buildings. In the viewpoint of the proposed system, all these flexibility provisions represent distributed energy resources in a wider sense. The system thus offers interoperable support for consumer-level integration of different energy systems (electricity, heat and gas), and additional flexibility sources are made available to the electric power system, all the time keeping the user comfort and avoiding service disruptions. The paper outlines the technical infrastructure as a backbone activating new sources of flexibility, helping the further proliferation of renewable energy sources and establishing new market actors.

Index Terms-- activation, democratization, demand response, flexibility, standards

I. INTRODUCTION

The complexity and the levels of uncertainty are generally increasing in the electric power system with time. The primary driver is the proliferation of renewable energy sources on the electric energy production side and mobility electrification on the consumption side. The system operator responsibilities typically include balancing the production and consumption, and the costs of balancing are carried over to the final consumer.

The deployment of renewables has been paired with abundant efforts dedicated to improving forecasting accuracy. These efforts, and particularly ones targeting improved forecast utility in the markets, as discussed in [1], surely mitigate a significant share of uncertainty-related issues. Perfect forecasting, however, is impossible, so ensuring affordable and abundant flexibility in the electric power system remains an issue.

Ensuring the balance of consumption and generation is one of the issues tackled by ancillary services, alongside issues such as redispatching, reactive power/voltage control and congestion management. Traditional approaches search for the required flexibility to provide, e.g., automatic and manual frequency restoration reserve (aFRR and mFRR, [2]) on the production side. Fast-ramping generation resources are commonly used: hydropower plants and gas-fired power plants able to start up quickly – however as many renewable sources are controllable to an extent through inverters, wind and solar power plants may be included as well [3].

Flexibility can be sought on the demand side as well: large energy consumers, such as steel or cement factories can offer the necessary flexibility that the system operator can activate when their primary process allows so. A further extension of this approach is to procure granular flexibility at the end-user premises level and activate the large pool of individually small, but collectively significant sources of flexibility. The primary process in question is then the individual user comfort when, e.g. heat pump load is being controlled.

For this to happen, software infrastructure and establishment of intermediary entities such as aggregators are required. The authors of [4] and [5] discuss a virtual power plant approach, using concepts similar to the one presented here. This paper presents a standards-based interoperable information system that supports activation and

democratization of flexibility over public communication networks. The paper departs from the scope of existing IEC 62746-10 standard and compounds it with other entities, required for deployment of a demand response flexibility solution.

II. OPENADR / IEC 62746-10

OpenADR (Open Automated Demand Response) [6] [7] is an open standard with a publicly available specification and architecture, designed by several US institutes and companies, later establishing the OpenADR Alliance, tasked with taking care of standard adoption and proliferation. Similarly to other American-originating standards, this one is also a *de facto* standard synthesized from practice – the first iteration was started during the Californian energy crisis of 2002 [8]. The second and current version of the standard has been linked to OASIS [9] energy interoperability standards. Within OpenADR 2.0, there is a reduced profile 2.0a and a more encompassing profile 2.0b. In Europe, IEC has fully adopted the OpenADR 2.0b standard as the IEC 62746-10: Open Automated Demand Response (OpenADR 2.0b Profile Specification) [10] in January 2019. In practice, this means the terms IEC 62746-10 and OpenADR 2.0b can be used interchangeably.

The encompassing IEC 62746 series of standards covers “Systems interface between customer energy management system and the power management system” – it defines the system interfaces and communication protocols covering the chain between a smart grid and smart home/building/industrial area. It specifies application-level service communication that can incentivize the responses from the customer-owned and customer-located distributed energy resources. Through price and demand response signals, provisioning of indirect control of customer-owned devices is enabled. The standard supports HTTP and XMPP as transport protocols, but actual “on the wire” transport mechanism is out of the scope of this standard. The messages are encoded in XML which indicates a relatively high overhead.

The IEC 62746-10 standard defines an open specification, intended to allow anyone the implementation of a two-way signaling system, providing the servers that publish information to the automated clients subscribing to the information. The standard covers the signaling data models and includes information related to specific DR electric reduction or shifting strategies taken at the facility. These resources may be managed as actual (physical) resources, as well as virtual resources that aggregate a set of capabilities of the physical.

The OpenADR specifications provide a minimal data model and services for DR, pricing, and distributed energy resource (DER) communications; a concise implementation of a two-way signalling system to facilitate information exchange between electricity service providers, aggregators and end users and a description of demand response signalling in terms of servers (virtual top nodes) that are publishing information to automated clients (virtual end nodes) being the subscribers of the information. In this context, aggregators [11] are mediators between the energy service entity responsible for balancing and procuring the flexibility – and the end users providing the actual flexibility.

III. VIRTUAL TOP NODES AND VIRTUAL END NODES

For a wider context and understanding several of the abstract concept OpenADR 2.0 utilizes, one should refer to the OASIS interoperability [9] and IEC 62939 – SGUI Smart Grid User Interface [12] standards. The SGUI aims to define the SGUI reference architecture, on how to build interfaces for diverse customer facility standards, all interacting with Smart Grid. Several ecosystems (energy, telecommunication, home automation) have been growing in coexistence separately sharing the location at the customer premise. SGUI defines services for symmetric interoperability between the service provider and end users. SGUI defines the Energy Service Interfaces (ESI) as an abstraction of SGUI for energy consumers and produces. The ESI is the surface where Energy Interoperation Services are exchanged. The ESI is the external face of the energy-consuming or supplying node. In terms of IEC 62939, a Resource (as used in Energy Interoperation) is any dispatchable logical entity that is dispatchable. The Resource is solely responsible for its own response, and its description specifies the performance envelope for a Resource. If a Resource can participate in multiple markets, it may have multiple descriptions (referring to the same technical unit. The Resource as in SGUI does not need to have a 1:1 mapping to the physical world. In market terms, a Resource is anything able to describe its capabilities in a Tender into a market.

This illustrates the abstract notion of OpenADR as such resources: controllable electric vehicle battery charges, stationary batteries whose battery management systems typically offer communication interface reliant on a variant of MQTT-based protocol and thus can receive setpoint control, heating, ventilation and air-conditioning systems (HVAC) that can exploit thermal inertia of buildings and control the operating point of heat pumps and many others – all these are completely valid examples of resources.

Figure 1. An illustration of a virtual top node and virtual end node concepts

The IEC 62939 covers the concepts of a virtual top node (VTN) and a virtual end node (VEN). The VEN has operational control of a set of resources and/or processes and can control the output or demand of these resources to affect their generation or utilization of electrical energy intelligently, in response to an understood set of smart grid messages. The VEN

may be either a producer or consumer of energy. The VEN can communicate (2-way) with a VTN, receiving and transmitting smart grid messages relaying grid situations, conditions, or events. In IEC 62939, the VTN is a party whose role is the aggregation of information and capabilities of distributed energy resources. A VEN entity in one context can be a VTN in another. VTNs and VENs may be structured in a tree-like hierarchy. Communication between VEN nodes at the same hierarchy levels is not supported. Figure 1 shows an illustration of the VTN and VEN concepts, where an aggregator takes the role of VTN when communicating with cooperatives, households and buildings in its portfolio, and at the same time, the aggregator is a VEN when communicating with the system operator.

IV. SEMANTIC INTERPRETATION OF PAYLOADS AND SCHEMA REQUIREMENT

The IEC 62746-10 standard is agnostic in relation to the DR load control strategies, as well as to the market-specific contractual or business agreements. The pragmatic approach to standard design is illustrated in service definition:

Register: identification of entities in advance of interactions with other parties;

- Event: generic core demand response event, providing event functions and information models for price-responsive DR;
- Report: this service enables feedback to provide either periodic or one-time information on the actual state of a resource and
- Opt: addressing the short-term changes in availability, providing the facility to communicate opt-in and opt-out schedules from virtual end nodes to virtual top nodes.

The simplicity of the above scheme ensures wide applicability – and at the same time, implementation details are left out. Literally, the standard defines how to carry the payload, but does not interpret its semantics. What is carried as information in a generic event isn't defined. Another example is the existence of aggregators. If there are no aggregators or there is a rule of exclusivity so there is a single aggregator, then there will be a single VTN all the resource VENs will communicate with. On the other hand, if multiple aggregators exist – then there will be multiple aggregator VTNs, seen from the viewpoint of a household or a building. The reporting is similarly generic – the definition of the report payload is implementation-specific.

The experiences in the implementation of various telecontrol protocols [13] in industrial automation indicate that it is crucial to ensure mutual understanding of all communication semantics. Currently, the most important standard in electric power engineering – the IEC 61850 – brings the formal semantics into industrial automation [14]. For this reason, the authors strongly recommend that the DR system designs and strictly enforces the communication schema on top of OpenADR for all the participants.

V. TELECONTROL PROTOCOLS AND RESOURCE REGISTRY

A key difference between telecontrol protocols such as IEC 60870 [15] [16] series of protocols and IEC 61850 on one side and OpenADR on the other is that OpenADR communication scheme is detached, while the other protocols have a direct control scheme. Among the four services, there is opt-in and opt-out: the resource owner can opt out of the demand response scheme. The control is thus indirect, while in, e.g. IEC 61850 it is more immediate and direct.

This means a gateway (software) device would be required to register as a VEN and convert the OpenADR message payloads to actual commands and actions on the direct control side. The gateway will interpret the events from, e.g. the 61850 side and pass the eventual unavailability information upwards to the OpenADR side.

The opt-in nature points out another requirement for the software infrastructure: the need for a demand response aggregator to implement its own registry to keep track of numerous end-users and their small-size resources.

VI. FLEXIBILITY BASELINE ESTIMATION AND DR RESOURCE HANDLING

As mentioned before, the demand response resources can be very diverse: stationary batteries, smart EV chargers, smart heat pumps, etc. Most of these resources have a primary service and flexibility provisioning should not impede the primary function [17]. For instance – in the case of electric vehicles, time arbitrage with charging point should not impede their primary transportation function [18] [19] [20]. Similarly, when larger thermal time constants of buildings are used as sources of inertia, the imperative is to keep the occupants comfortable even when the heat pump operational point is not where it would ideally be [21]. Estimating the amount of flexibility available is by no means a trivial task – and properly forecasting such flexibility is an even harder one.

A typical approach is to gather sensor measurements from the end-user premises and get the feedback information about eventual discomfort from the willing users. This estimates the baseline needs and coupled with the actual energy usage, this provides an estimate of available flexibility [22] [23] [24]. This is a notably sensitive area as end-user data must be securely processed in accordance with European Union recent strict legislation – and this is a topic of current interdisciplinary research.

In technical terms, this means a user premises device is required to gather the sensor measurements and to communicate upwards to the middleware. Similarly to the situation with telecontrol protocols, the same device has to handle a number of in-house devices that can provide flexibility: HVAC, lightning device, domestic hot water, photovoltaic systems, batteries installed in residential buildings, etc.

There is a number of in-house protocols [7] [25] such as ZigBee, Bluetooth Low Energy, Z-Wave, EnOcean and Insteon. PV inverter devices and batteries often use custom protocols exposing an HTTP or MQTT interface. The role of an

in-house device is thus to act as a gateway to and from these devices.

VII. CYBER SECURITY REQUIREMENTS

Most automation protocols have been designed with dedicated communication channels in mind. It is not reasonable to expect such configuration with DR infrastructure: it is expected for the communication to happen over the public network instead.

One can expect malicious actors to tamper with communication, so security has to be ensured properly. The OpenADR standard does not define transport mechanisms and only covers minimum cybersecurity mechanisms required to provide non-repudiation and mitigation of cyber-security risks. The standard defines that public key infrastructure has to be utilized and that security should be implemented via transport layer security (TLS) to ensure secure communication between VTNs and VENs. As a minimum, the standard requires ECC keys longer than 256 bytes and RSA keys longer than 2048 bits. The certificates must be of X.509v3 type.

The actual PKI infrastructure provider is left to the implementer – certification services provider can be international, national or local. The standard only defines the procedure of fingerprint-based verification of the other party and XML messages signing. In short – to deploy a successful demand response infrastructure based on OpenADR, a working PKI infrastructure is an absolute must.

The standard itself does not cover how the end users (the actual persons owning the DR resources) authenticate and have access to the system granted. This is an external functionality that is necessary for the end users to be able to monitor their participation.

VIII. THE PROPOSED ARCHITECTURE OUTLINE

Figure 2 depicts the proposed technical architecture, according to the issues described in previous chapters.

The flexibility user – typically the network operator, or another type of balance responsible party, depending on the market organization, utilizes OpenADR (with the overlaid enforced semantic schema) to communicate with the flexibility aggregators. Though only a single aggregator is depicted, multiple flexibility aggregators can coexist – it also depends on the market organization. All the aggregators can effectively disappear – then each gateway is fused with its own “aggregator”, then the flexibility user communicates directly with the gateways.

The aggregator, in turn, communicates with a single or a set of gateways. There are two types of gateways - both with similar purposes, yet with very different implementations. Telecontrol gateway handles larger DR resources converting OpenADR messages to direct control messages and passing the information on the status upwards. Home gateway, on the other hand, similarly passes the activation messages downward and gathers the sensor data and passes it upwards to the “aggregator middleware”.

The aggregator middleware consists of three key parts: registry of users and resources, the aggregator itself, and the

end-user accessible software. The end-user software enables the end users to perform business interactions with the aggregator, e.g. to visualize the data, to see the billing records, to terminate the contract, etc. The registry, as described in chapter V above, keeps track of all the DR resources and pairs them with end users for the purposes of billing. The key aggregator software is the business logic of an aggregator: it optimizes the market participation and bids the flexibility according to optimization results [26] [27] [28].

Figure 2. Illustration of the proposed demand response architecture

While the central aggregator scheme is easier to understand, the above is usable in peer-to-peer trading as well. The aggregator in that setting can become distributed: as distributed tracking comes into play and assumes the role of a centralized aggregator and registry.

Finally, the red frame defines the secure infrastructure, secured by PKI. The dashed line indicates that within the house or on the dedicated lines designed for IEC 61850 it may be impossible to implement. However, the internal network is also vulnerable to spoofing: for instance, impersonation of the “home controller box” resulting in unwanted actions. These can have a direct impact on user comfort so the authors strongly suggest that the home network is also considered vulnerable and that it should be secured properly. Similarly, as telecontrol gateway represents a link to the public internet, securing of internal links is also strongly recommended.

IX. CONCLUSIONS

The paper outlines an implementation of standards-based infrastructure for active demand response. The presented infrastructure is a synthesized and abstracted result of several efforts to implement the DR infrastructure. The proposed system follows the paradigm of a shared and common electric distribution network infrastructure - but does not impose a classic centralized market organization. New market actors such as flexibility aggregators can be established on top of the proposed software infrastructure as well. The mapping between the detached communication scheme of OpenADR/IEC 62746 to direct control standards such as IEC 61850 is discussed, as well as the actual implementation of home automation interfaces on the end-user premises.

The primary driver for the deployment of active demand response systems is twofold: activation of new sources of flexibility to balance the variability coming from renewables, and at the same time lessening the flexibility cost burden of the end users, by including their resources directly in the flexibility activation. Coupled with an appropriate business complement such as remuneration scheme, the proposed technical architecture can reach both goals.

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